

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF DISCOUNTED CASH FLOW AND RELATIVE VALUATION METHODS IN INDONESIAN TECHNOLOGY COMPANIES

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Abstract

This study aims to calculate the intrinsic value of technology companies using the Discounted Cash Flow - Free Cash Flow to Firm (FCFF) method and Relative Valuation methods, namely the Price to Earnings Ratio (PER) and Price to Book Value (PBV), under three growth scenarios: pessimistic, moderate, and optimistic. It also seeks to analyze which valuation method is more accurate for determining the fair value of stocks, particularly in the technology sector. The object of this research is companies in the Software and IT Services subsector listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX). The results using the Discounted Cash Flow (DCF) method indicate that technology stocks are undervalued across all scenarios compared to market prices. Similarly, the Relative Valuation results mostly show that stocks are undervalued under all scenarios when compared to the industry average of the technology sector's software and IT services subsector. The study also reveals that the most accurate valuation method is Relative Valuation, as indicated by a smaller Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) value.

Keywords: Technology Companies, Valuation, Intrinsic Value, Discounted Cash Flow, Relative Valuation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of technology and digital economy in Indonesia, especially since the Covid-19 pandemic, has been very rapid. Based on data from the Indonesian Internet Service Providers Association, internet users have also continued to show a positive trend since the pandemic, 73.7% of the total population increased to 79.5%. Based on data from the Coordinating Ministry for Economic Affairs of the Republic of Indonesia as of August 1, 2024, Indonesia has several achievements at the global level such as: having the most innovative startups or ranking 1st in ASEAN, and having 15 unicorns and 2 decacorns that have gone global. Indonesia is also ranked the 2nd country with the largest digital investment destination in ASEAN or USD 21.97 billion, where e-commerce accounts for 40% of the market share in ASEAN. Since 2020, 29 technology companies have also conducted Initial Public Offerings (IPOs) on the Indonesia Stock Exchange, 22 of which are companies in the software/software subsector. This number is 2 times higher than the previous 10 years (2010-2019). On the other hand, the performance of Indonesian technology company stocks included in IDXTECHNO has shown a negative or declining trend since 2022 until now. Based on data from IDX Daily Statistics as of September 13, 2024, IDXTECHNO even has the lowest performance among all sectoral indices, namely -12.93% YTD. The performance of Indonesian technology stocks had experienced extraordinary growth in 2021, IDXTECHNO increased by 707.6% while JCI increased by only 10.1%, and LQ45 decreased by 0.4%. However, since 2022, IDXTECHNO has continued to decline until 2024 by -42.6%, -14.1%, and -25.9%, respectively. (IDXTECHNO, 2024). This phenomenon is certainly not in line with the current conditions in

the technology market and efforts to advance technology in Indonesia. In the ASEAN market, it analyzes the comparative performance of technology and communication companies in ASEAN countries, where the analysis shows varying results in each financial ratio, namely current ratio, solvency, and profitability. The countries with unhealthy current ratios are Vietnam and the Philippines; the country with an unhealthy solvency ratio is Vietnam; countries with unhealthy and very unhealthy profitability ratios are Malaysia, Singapore, Thailand, and Indonesia. It can be concluded that profitability is indeed a challenge for the technology sector in various countries in ASEAN which has an impact on investor response which is reflected in IDXTECHNO's share price in the portfolio. Achjari & Suryaningrum (2024) Widiantari et al (2024) Conducting research on the analysis of the digital economy and blockchain technology on the return of technology stocks, it was found that the analysis of the digital economy measured by the number of monthly active users and income has a positive and significant effect on stock returns. Therefore, an in-depth and comprehensive analysis of the intrinsic value or fair value of technology company shares is needed to find out whether Indonesian technology companies are undervalued, fair-valued, or overvalued by the market, as well as analyze the most accurate valuation method to calculate the company's intrinsic value.

2. LITERATURE STUDIES

The selection of an appropriate valuation method depends largely on the characteristics of the company, the purpose of the analysis, and the market context (Damodaran, 2014). There are three common valuation methods: discounted cash flow valuation, in which cash flows are adjusted for risk; relative valuation, which determines the value of an asset based on comparable assets; and contingent claim valuation, in which the option-like characteristics of an asset are valued using an option pricing model (Damodaran, 2014).

Susanto & Rahadian (2021) calculated the intrinsic value of shares of animal feed subsector companies in Indonesia in 2018 using the free cash flow to firm (FCFF) approach and relative valuation based on price to earning ratio (PER) and price book value (PBV) and with pessimistic, moderate, and optimistic scenarios. The discounted cash flow (DCF)-FCFF valuation results show that Charoen Phokpand Indonesia (CPIN) shares in the pessimistic and moderate scenarios are overvalued, while in the optimistic scenario they are undervalued.

Japfa Comfeed Indonesia (JPFA) shares are undervalued in all scenarios, and Malindo Feedmill (MAIN) shares are overvalued in all scenarios. The PER valuation results show that CPIN shares in the pessimistic and moderate scenarios are undervalued, while in the optimistic scenario they are overvalued. JPFA and MAIN shares in all scenarios are overvalued. The PBV valuation results show that CPIN shares in the scenario are undervalued, while in the moderate and optimistic scenarios are overvalued. JPFA and MAIN shares in all scenarios are overvalued. Hutapea & Salim (2022) analyzed the determination of the fair price of Indonesian companies such as PT H.M. Sampoerna Tbk (HMSP), PT Gudang Garam Tbk (GGRM), PT Indonesian Tobacco Tbk (ITIC) using the Free Cash Flow to Firm (FCFF) and Relative Valuation approaches. The results showed that HMSP equity was overvalued with a negative

Return on Investment (ROI), GGRM equity was overvalued in some scenarios and undervalued in others, while ITIC equity was undervalued in moderate and optimistic scenarios, and overvalued in pessimistic scenarios.

Sunandar & Salim (2023) analyzed the valuation of the retail sector in Indonesia. The results showed that using the DCF-FCFF method in a moderate scenario, the intrinsic value of PT Sumber Alfaria Trijaya Tbk, PT Midi Utama Indonesia Tbk, PT Enseval Putera Megatrading Tbk, and PT Diamond Food Indonesia Tbk was overvalued, while PT Millennium Pharmacon International Tbk was undervalued. RV-PER and RV-PBV methods in a moderate scenario, the shares of PT Sumber Alfaria Trijaya Tbk, PT Enseval Putera Megatrading Tbk, and PT Millennium Pharmacon International Tbk are considered undervalued, while PT Midi Utama Indonesia Tbk and PT Diamond Food Indonesia Tbk look expensive.

2.1 Discounted Cash Flow

The discounted cash flow model is a method used to estimate the value of a company by looking at four main factors: current cash flow, expected growth rate, terminal value, and discount rate used to calculate the present value of that cash flow. (Damodaran, 2012)

2.2 Free Cash Flow to Firm (FCFF)

Free Cash Flow to Firm is the cash flow available to all capital providers after deducting operating expenses from income and adding back non-cash items such as depreciation and amortization. Mathematically to calculate the FCFF value is as follows: (Damodaran, 2012)

$$\text{FCFF} = \text{EBIT} (1 - \text{Tax Rate}) + \text{Depreciation} - \text{Capital Expenditure} - \Delta \text{Working Capital}$$

Mathematically to calculate the value of a company is as follows:

$$\text{Value of Firm} = \sum_{t=1}^{t=n} \frac{\text{CF to Firm}_t}{(1 + \text{WACC})^t}$$

Cost of capital is generally calculated based on the Weighted Average Cost of Capital – WACC (Damodaran, 2014). The formula for calculating WACC is:

$$\text{WACC} = \left(\frac{E}{V}\right) K_e + K_p \left(\frac{P}{V}\right) + K_d (1 - T) \left(\frac{D}{V}\right)$$

Terminal Value is used to calculate the estimated growth or growth rate of a company after a certain period, where the company's growth rate is estimated to be stable or equivalent to the economic growth rate in which the company is located (Damodaran, 2014).

The formula for calculating the Terminal Value is:

$$\text{Terminal Value} = \frac{\text{Free Cash Flow to Firm}_{n+1}}{(r_n - g_n)}$$

2.3 Relative Valuation

In relative valuation, the value of an asset is determined by comparing it to similar assets or companies in the same industry, which are adjusted using common factors such as cash flow,

book value, or revenue. (Damodaran, 2014) Commonly used methods are the industry-standard Price to Earning Ratio and Price to Book Value for valuing a company, assuming that other companies in the same industry are similar to the one being evaluated and that the market typically rates these companies accurately. Damodaran, 2014)

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Population & Sample

The object of this research is a technology company in the Software and IT Services subsector that is included in the TECHNO index listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange as many as 5 companies out of 35 companies with the purposive sampling method. The companies that are sampled in this study are Elang Mahkota Teknologi Tbk (EMTK), Multipolar Technology Tbk (MLPT), Anabatic Technologies Tbk (ATIC), NFC Indonesia Tbk (NFCX), and Digital Mediatama Maxima Tbk (DMMX).

3.2 Data Collection

The historical data used to analyze the company's revenue growth is historical data for 2019-2023 for the 2024-2028 projection. Stock prices and the Composite Stock Price Index (JCI) were obtained from Yahoo Finance through the www.yahooofinance.com website. Bank Indonesia's interest rate obtained from the www.bi.go.id website.

3.3 Data Analysis Techniques – DCF FCFF

- 1) Analyze historical performance. Analyze revenue, operating expenses, depreciation and amortization, taxes, capital costs, and net working capital during 2019-2023 which will be used as the basis for performance projections for the upcoming 2024-2028.
- 2) Projection on Future Performance. Determine the growth rate by means of sustainable growth and reinvestment growth.
- 3) Calculating WACC. The cost of capital is calculated using the CAPM (Capital Asset Pricing Model) method, while the cost of debt is calculated by analyzing the amount of debt that is interest-bearing with the interest rate charged to the company. To calculate the CAPM value or capital cost, the market return used is the market price or JCI in 2023; risk-free rate using the BI Rate in 2023; Beta uses the company's historical stock price for 5 years (2019-2023).
- 4) Calculating Free Cash Flow to the Firm. Calculate the company's free cash flow projections for 2024-2028 in optimistic, moderate, and pessimistic scenarios.
- 5) Calculating the Terminal Value. Calculates the present value of all future cash flows earned after 2028.
- 6) Calculating Enterprise Value. Calculate the present value of the company's total free cash flow for the 2022-2028 period plus the present value of free cash flows after 2028 with terminal value.

- 7) Calculating Equity Value. Calculates the value of equity based on the formula: Equity Value = Enterprise Value – Total Debt + Cash & Cash Equivalents.
- 8) Calculating the fair value of the company's shares. Calculate the fair value of shares by dividing the value of equity by the number of outstanding shares, based on optimistic, moderate, and pessimistic scenarios.

3.4 Data Analysis Techniques – PER

The calculation of intrinsic value by the relative valuation method in this study uses a fundamental approach, where this approach is based on the company's intrinsic value (equity value) obtained from earning growth rates and cash flows (Damodaran, 2012). The approach used to calculate PER is the forward P/E approach, which is calculated by dividing the stock price by the expected future earnings per share (Wahlen, et.al, 2022).

3.5 Data Analysis Techniques – PBV

The intrinsic value of PBV is calculated by dividing the equity value by the book value of equity (Damodaran, 2012), where the book value of equity is obtained from the company's financial statements.

3.6 Comparative Analysis Techniques

The results of the calculation of the intrinsic value are compared with market prices and industry averages in the technology sector. The criteria for comparing intrinsic value with the market and industry can be seen in the table below:

Table 1: Criteria for Comparison of Intrinsic Value with Market and Industrial Prices

Method	Condition	Analysis
DCF	Intrinsic Value < Stock Market Price	Overvalued
	Intrinsic value = stock market price	Fair-valued
	Intrinsic Value > Stock Market Price	Undervalued
RV-PER	Intrinsic Value PER > avg PER industry	Overvalued
	Intrinsic value PER = avg PER industry	Fair-valued
	Intrinsic Value PER < avg PER industry	Undervalued
RV - PBV	Intrinsic Value of PBV > avg Industrial PBV	Overvalued
	Intrinsic value of PBV = avg of industrial PBV	Fair-valued
	Intrinsic value of PBV < avg PBV industry	Undervalued

Comparative analysis of valuation methods using Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), to find out the difference between the actual value and the predicted value (Afrianto, 2013). A method is said to be more accurate if it produces a small RMSE value, so that the smaller the RMSE value obtained, the more accurate the prediction is (Afrianto, 2013).

$$RMSE = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (Y_i - O_i)^2}}{n}$$

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Historical Analysis

PT Elang Mahkota Teknologi Tbk (EMTK)

Historical analysis was carried out to determine the company's performance and as a basis for calculating the projections for 2024-2028 as shown in table 3 below:

Table 2: Historical Performance of EMTK (in thousands of rupiahs)

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Avg
Revenue	11,030,044,792	11,936,381,982	12,840,734,345	15,524,642,337	9,241,419,373	
Revenue Growth	23.11%	8.22%	7.58%	20.90%	-40.47%	3.9%
COGS	8,144,754,189	8,930,352,096	8,929,479,459	11,947,374,741	6,198,842,164	73.93%
OPEX	1,699,973,688	1,494,648,763	2,094,504,550	2,576,341,897	2,608,800,800	15.32%
Depreciation	319,508,802	286,066,275	467,039,208	470,462,082	487,319,810	3.01%
EBIT	865,808,113	1,225,314,848	1,349,711,128	530,463,617	-53,543,401	7.74%
Capex	827,673,279	235,568,620	382,183,398	454,434,987	720,856,671	3.70%
Change in working capital	-1,628,263,790	-1,451,761,555	5,282,101,750	3,626,843,195	-757,407,000	11.36%

Based on table 2, there will be a decrease in revenue in 2023 because EMTK relinquished 100% ownership of PT SS with revenue of 5 trillion, resulting in an average growth in the company's revenue of 3.9%. Due to the anomaly data for 2023, the basis for calculating growth uses data from 2019-2022, so that an average growth of 14.95% is obtained. Then, the proportion of cost of goods sold to revenue is 73.93%, Opex to revenue is 15.32%, depreciation and amortization to revenue is 3.01%, CAPEX to revenue is 3.70%.

PT NFC Indonesia Tbk (NFCX)

Historical analysis was carried out to determine the company's performance and as a basis for calculating the projections for 2024-2028 as shown in table 4 below:

Table 3: NFCX Historical Performance

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Avg
Revenue	6,153,637,893	7,597,266,302	8,885,891,410	9,836,622,375	9,526,101,866	
Revenue Growth	147.17%	23.46%	16.96%	10.70%	-3.16%	39.0%
COGS	6,044,438,130	7,490,222,004	8,751,463,663	9,688,602,492	9,347,522,813	98.42%
OPEX	42,898,282	36,705,581	52,014,662	81,044,350	100,434,640	0.75%
Depreciation	1,477,981	9,493,402	22,904,706	40,971,911	59,679,427	0.37%
EBIT	64,823,501	60,845,315	59,508,379	26,003,622	18,464,986	0.46%
Capex	17,013,430	176,589,239	61,583,286	55,447,943	93,778,162	1.08%
Change in Working Capital	538,387,153	-194,843,562	315,241,786	-106,811,714	-481,015,512	-1.30%

There was tremendous growth in 2019 in NFCX revenue post-IPO in 2018 as well as driven by post-Covid-19 growth in technology & digitalization, so that the average NFCX growth was 39.0%. Due to the post-IPO growth anomaly, this growth base uses historical data from 2020 to 2023, so that the company's average growth is 11.99%. Then, the proportion of cost of goods

sold to revenue is 98.42%, Opex to revenue is 0.75%, depreciation and amortization to revenue is 0.37%, CAPEX to revenue is 1.08%.

PT Digital Mediatama Maxima Tbk (DMMX)

Historical analysis was carried out to determine the company's performance and as a basis for calculating the projections for 2024-2028 as shown in table 4 below:

Table 4: Historical Performance of DMMX (in thousands of rupiahs)

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Avg
Revenue	211,001,743	517,197,998	1,150,441,213	1,938,153,436	1,945,055,731	
Revenue Growth	260.38%	145.12%	122.44%	68.47%	0.36%	119.35%
COGS	185,264,029	465,791,148	1,069,192,185	1,844,755,323	1,828,240,581	93.82%
Opex	13,104,178	21,953,807	34,401,462	46,374,655	47,234,279	2.70%
Depreciation	391,945	3,867,702	16,185,240	31,714,203	45,877,118	1.76%
EBIT	12,241,590	25,585,342	30,662,327	15,309,256	23,703,752	1.72%
Capex	10,764,856	148,578,509	46,442,947	35,870,583	59,986,497	5.24%
Change in Working Capital	642,082,360	-117,149,145	209,927,379	-84,916,165	-383,024,701	-6.76%

Based on table 4, it can be seen that DMMX's revenue trend experienced a tremendous increase after the IPO in 2019, as well as the growth of technology & digitalization after Covid-19, resulting in an average DMMX growth of 119.35%. Because the growth is very high, a recalculation of DMMX's revenue growth is carried out using the reinvestment rate method. The reinvestment rate method is a method to calculate the company's revenue growth with new investments (Damodaran, 2014). Calculate revenue growth using the formula:

$$\text{Expected Growth} = \text{Reinvestment rate} \times \text{Return on capital}$$

DMMX's average revenue growth was 11.59%. Then, the proportion of cost of goods sold to revenue is 93.82%, Opex to revenue is 2.70%, depreciation and amortization to revenue is 1.76%, CAPEX to revenue is 5.24%.

PT Multipolar Technology Tbk (MLPT)

Historical analysis was carried out to determine the company's performance and as a basis for calculating the projection for 2024-2028 as shown in table 5 below:

Table 5: MLPT's Historical Performance (in thousands of rupiahs)

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Avg
Revenue	2,455,526,000	2,685,797,000	2,996,710,000	3,442,223,000	3,297,221,000	
Revenue Growth	0.82%	9.38%	11.58%	14.87%	-4.21%	6.49%
COGS	1,979,803,000	2,165,890,000	2,420,507,000	2,750,500,000	2,579,213,000	79.96%
Opex	160,845,000	158,495,000	134,726,000	242,245,000	226,137,000	6.20%
Depreciation	132,781,000	159,627,000	150,371,000	138,799,000	194,122,000	5.21%
EBIT	182,097,000	201,785,000	291,106,000	310,679,000	297,749,000	8.63%
Capex	318,750,000	99,440,000	117,583,000	188,690,000	515,868,000	8.34%
Change in Working Capital	-91,918,000	-12,732,000	20,468,000	40,165,000	-378,673,000	-2.84%

Table 5 shows that the trend of MLPT's revenue has increased from 2019 to 2022, but has decreased by 4.21% in 2023, resulting in an average revenue growth of 6.49%. While the proportion of cost of goods sold to revenue is 79.96%, Opex to revenue is 6.20%, depreciation and amortization to revenue is 5.21%, CAPEX to revenue is 8.34%.

PT Anabatic Technologies Tbk (ATIC)

Historical analysis was carried out to determine the company's performance and as a basis for calculating projections for 2024-2028 as shown in table 6 below:

Table 6: ATIC Historical Performance (in thousands of rupiahs)

	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	Avg
Revenue	5,578,438,213	6,157,619,315	6,459,797,692	7,809,976,522	10,207,024,937	
Revenue Growth	2.67%	10.38%	4.91%	20.90%	30.69%	13.91%
COGS	4,675,392,465	5,157,107,347	5,477,953,880	6,799,430,336	8,975,960,929	85.84%
OPEX	903,045,748	1,000,511,968	981,843,812	1,010,546,186	1,231,064,008	14.16%
Depreciation	61,388,556	60,958,831	43,554,433	40,175,102	37,998,351	0.67%
EBIT	242,106,758	158,701,993	98,832,064	365,735,727	543,441,161	3.89%
Capex	116,487,077	90,866,463	21,940,809	14,967,513	34,051,098	0.77%
Change in Working Capital	-539,677,266	-507,720,879	-357,891,497	63,829,416	623,370,456	-0.58%

The ATIC revenue trend since 2019 has increased until 2023 with an average growth during that period of 13.91%. While the proportion of cost of goods sold to revenue is 85.84%, OPEX to revenue is 14.16%, depreciation and amortization to revenue is 0.67%, CAPEX to revenue is 0.77%.

4.2 Growth Projections

Due to the uncertainty of the company's future growth, assumptions and projections are built with pessimistic, moderate, and optimistic scenarios. (Adrianov & Hendrawan (2023). In an optimistic scenario with positive spreads, revenue growth is calculated by adding the company's historical average by 0.5 the spread between the company's and industry's historical averages; Meanwhile, if the spread is negative, then the optimistic condition uses the average growth of the industry. In a moderate scenario, revenue growth is calculated using the company's historical average. In a pessimistic scenario with positive spreads, revenue growth is calculated using the historical average of industry growth; While negative spreads use the company's historical average plus 0.5 spreads between the industry and company averages.

Table 7: Company Growth Scenario

Stock	Avg Corporate Growth	Avg Industry Growth	Spread	Growth Scenario		
				Pessimistic	Moderate	Optimistic
EMTK	14.95%	11.67%	-3.28%	11.67%	14.95%	16.59%
NFCX	11.99%		0.32%	11.67%	11.99%	12.15%
DMMX	11.59%		-0.08%	11.56%	11.59%	11.67%
MLPT	6.49%		-5.19%	3.89%	6.49%	11.67%
ATIC	13.91%		2.24%	11.67%	13.91%	15.03%

Based on table 7, the projected revenue growth of each company is obtained in pessimistic, moderate, and optimistic scenarios to calculate valuation using DCF-FCFF. Next, calculate the intrinsic value per share by the number of outstanding shares of each company.

4.3 Analysis of Valuation Results

4.3.1 Intrinsic Value Analysis of DCF-FCFF Method with Market Value

The market value is obtained from the closing price of each company's shares as of December 29, 2023. The detailed valuation results can be seen in the following table 8:

Table 8: Comparison of the Intrinsic Value of the DCF-FCFF Method with the Market Value

Issuer	Scenario	Intrinsic Value	Market Value (Dec 29, 2023)	Comparison Results
EMTK	Pessimist	IDR321	IDR590	Overvalued
	Moderate	IDR624		Undervalued
	Optimistic	IDR 1,291		Undervalued
NFCX	Pessimist	IDR8,867	IDR 4,050	Undervalued
	Moderate	IDR 9,475		Undervalued
	Optimistic	IDR 9,804		Undervalued
DMMX	Pessimist	IDR780	IDR314	Undervalued
	Moderate	IDR785		Undervalued
	Optimistic	Rp797		Undervalued
MLPT	Pessimist	IDR 1,435	IDR 1,570	Overvalued
	Moderate	IDR2,177		Undervalued
	Optimistic	IDR 5,093		Undervalued
ATIC	Pessimist	IDR7,926	IDR 500	Undervalued
	Moderate	IDR13,629		Undervalued
	Optimistic	IDR19,147		Undervalued

Based on table 8, it can be seen that the results of the comparison between the market value and the intrinsic value of each company's shares with the three scenarios show different results.

However, most markets value shares of Indonesian technology companies below intrinsic or undervalued prices. In the optimistic and moderate scenarios, the comparison results show that all technology stocks are undervalued by the market.

Meanwhile, in the pessimistic scenario, the comparison results show that EMTK and MLPT shares are considered overvalued by the market, while other company shares are considered undervalued. This indicates that the market has high expectations for EMTK and MLPT at a pessimistic to moderate growth rate.

4.3.2 Analysis of the Intrinsic Value of the RV-PER Method with Industry Average Value

The average value of the industry is obtained the actual PER value of similar companies in 2023. Here's a detailed comparison of intrinsic PER values with industry average PER values:

Table 9: Comparison of the Intrinsic Value of the RV-PER Method with the Industry Average

Issuer	Scenario	Intrinsic Value	Industrial P/E Dec 29, 2023			Comparison
		P/E Forward	Min	Avg	Max	
EMTK	Pessimist	32	-160	42	409	Overvalued
	Moderate	60				Undervalued
	Optimistic	127				Undervalued
NFCX	Pessimist	85	-160	42	409	Undervalued
	Moderate	164				Undervalued
	Optimistic	169				Undervalued
DMMX	Pessimist	195	-160	42	409	Undervalued
	Moderate	196				Undervalued
	Optimistic	199				Undervalued
MLPT	Pessimist	12	-160	42	409	Overvalued
	Moderate	17				Overvalued
	Optimistic	39				Overvalued
ATIC	Pessimist	53	-160	42	409	Undervalued
	Moderate	89				Undervalued
	Optimistic	124				Undervalued

The comparison results show that most of the sample companies' PER is undervalued compared to the average PER of the Software and IT services sub-sector industry listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. The results of the comparison of the RV-PER method are in accordance with the results of the comparison of the DCF-FCFF method to the market value. Where most investors assess the undervalued shares of Indonesian technology companies. There are several issuers that have an overvalued PER value compared to the industry average PER, namely EMTK in pessimistic scenarios, then MLPT in all scenarios.

4.3.3 Analysis of the Intrinsic Value of the RV-PBV Method with Industry Average Value

The average value of the industry is obtained the actual PBV value of similar companies in 2023. The following is a detailed comparison of the intrinsic PBV value with the industry average PBV value:

Table 10: Comparison of the Intrinsic Value of the RV-PBV Method with the Industry Average

Issuer	Scenario	Intrinsic Value	Industrial PBV			Comparison
		PBV	Min	Avg	Max	
EMTK	Pessimist	0.51	0.26	2.46	5.86	Overvalued
	Moderate	1.00				Overvalued
	Optimistic	2.06				Overvalued
NFCX	Pessimist	6.58	0.26	2.46	5.86	Undervalued
	Moderate	7.04				Undervalued
	Optimistic	7.28				Undervalued
DMMX	Pessimist	8.40	0.26	2.46	5.86	Undervalued
	Moderate	8.46				Undervalued
	Optimistic	8.58				Undervalued
MLPT	Pessimist	3.77	0.26	2.46	5.86	Undervalued

	Moderate	5.72				Undervalued
	Optimistic	13.38				Undervalued
ATIC	Pessimist	46.66	0.26	2.46	5.86	Undervalued
	Moderate	80.22				Undervalued
	Optimistic	112.70				Undervalued

Based on the table above, the comparison of the average industrial PBV with the intrinsic value of PBV shows different results. The results of the comparison show that most of the intrinsic value of the PBV of the sample companies is considered undervalued compared to the average value of the PBV of the Software and IT Services sub-sector industry listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. The results of this RV-PBV comparison show that industrially, the market values technology sector stocks as undervalued, which indicates that investors have low expectations for the growth of the technology sector. These results are also in accordance with the comparison of company values using the DCF-FCFF and RV-PER methods, where most of the results of the comparison of intrinsic value with market value and industry average are undervalued.

4.4 Comparative Analysis of Valuation Methods

A comparison of valuation methods is carried out to find out the most accurate method to calculate the intrinsic value of a stock or company. The comparative analysis was calculated using the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE). The valuation method is said to be more accurate if the RMSE figure between the intrinsic value and the market value and the industry average is getting smaller.

Table 11: Comparison Results of Valuation Methods

Issuer	Scenario	RMSE Value		
		DCF -FCFF	RV-PER	RV-PBV
EMTK	Pessimist	59,525	36,673	0
	Moderate	2,947	318	2
	Optimistic	491,230	79,209	14
NFCX	Pessimist	25,266,083	60,061	40
	Moderate	29,429,063	14,921	21
	Optimistic	31,405,558	57,142	2
DMMX	Pessimist	276,176	125,832	66
	Moderate	280,033	23,807	36
	Optimistic	232,998	43,942	7
MLPT	Pessimist	16,983	29,435	12
	Moderate	368,387	605	11
	Optimistic	12,343,999	136,894	57
ATIC	Pessimist	55,897,099	45,350	2,152
	Moderate	172,631,061	2,262	6,047
	Optimistic	345,290,256	80,716	11,415
RMSE Value		44,932,760	49,144	1,326

Based on the comparison table above, it is known that the RV-PBV method has the lowest RMSE value compared to the DCF-FCFF and RV-PER methods. The RMSE value of the Relative Valuation method is also lower than the Discounted Cash Flow method. So based on

RMSE calculations, the most accurate method to calculate the intrinsic value of technology companies in the software and IT services subsector for the 2024-2028 projection period is the Relative Valuation method.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on historical analysis, projection calculations, and comparative analysis conducted previously, the following research conclusions were obtained:

1. The valuation results using the Discounted Cash Flow method, The Free Cash Flow approach showed that EMTK and MLPT shares in a pessimistic scenario were overvalued by the market, while in a moderate and optimistic scenario the market was considered undervalued. Meanwhile, the company's other stocks, namely NFCX, DMMX, and ATIC are considered undervalued in all scenarios.
2. The valuation results using the Relative Valuation method of the PER and PBV approach show the following results:
 - a) The valuation results using the Relative Valuation method of the PER approach showed that the PER MLPT values in all scenarios were overvalued compared to the industry average; the EMTK PER values were overvalued in pessimistic scenarios, while moderate and optimistic scenarios were undervalued compared to the industry averages; the values of PER NFCX, ATIC, & DMMX in all scenarios were undervalued.
 - b) The valuation results using the Relative Valuation method of the PBV approach show that the value of the PBV of EMTK in all scenarios is overvalued compared to the industry average. Meanwhile, the PBV ratios of other issuers are NFCX, DMMX, MLPT, and ATIC in all scenarios undervalued compared to the industry average.
3. The results of the valuation comparison with the market and the industry average using both methods showed similar results, where the two methods mostly showed that the shares of technology companies in the software and IT services subsectors were undervalued by the market and compared to the industry average. However, based on the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) comparison method of the two methods, it was found that the Relative Valuation method has a smaller RMSE value, so it can be concluded that Relative Valuation is more accurate to calculate the fair or intrinsic value of shares of technology companies in the software and IT services subsector for the 2024-2028 projection.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Valuation aims to calculate the value of a company based on fundamental aspects of the company. This study describes each of the company's historical performance, intrinsic value, and market perception of the company as reflected in the stock price and industry average. There are several companies that are considered overvalued and undervalued by the market and industry. However, most market and industry perceptions are still low towards technology companies, this is marked by the fact that most of the valuation results in DCF-FCFF and RV-

PER and RV-PBV are undervalued. The performance of company shares is certainly a concern for the company's managers. Therefore, companies need to develop strategies to improve company performance, especially after the pandemic, where the decline in stock prices or the growth rate of technology companies' revenue continues to show a downward growth trend. At the peak of 2023, the technology sector's revenue growth rate declined year-on-year (YoY) by -11.88%. Therefore, the company must maximize working capital and Capex to increase the company's revenue and profitability, as well as continue to innovate and develop technology products to create products that suit customer needs, which can ultimately increase revenue and sustainability in the long run.

Analysis of the technology industry globally shows that the technology sector is experiencing an upward trend in stock prices. Meanwhile, in Indonesia, the trend of technology stock price movements is still showing a decline until 2023 since 2019. This study analyzes the intrinsic value of technology companies in the software and IT services subsector in Indonesia listed on the IDX, where most of the results show that technology sector stocks are still cheap or undervalued when compared to their intrinsic value calculated using the DCF-FCFF and Relative Valuation methods. Therefore, investors can consider the fundamentals and projections of technology growth in the long term as a reference in investing.

This study has research limitations in historical analysis, projection and valuation calculations, and analysis of valuation methods carried out. The historical analysis uses historical data from 2019-2023 where the period is a pandemic and post-pandemic, so that it affects growth, Capex, and working capital, which will ultimately affect the company's valuation. Therefore, researchers can then use different and more accurate methods of calculating growth and terminal growth. Since this study compares valuation methods, the researcher is then advised to use other valuation methods and different comparison methods (different tests) in addition to the RMSE method to test a more accurate valuation method.

Declaration of interest statement

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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